

Survey of Cross River Gorilla (*Gorilla gorilla diehli*) in Cross-River National Park, Cross River State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This research surveyed the park in order to know the areas of occurrence of Cross River Gorilla (*Gorilla gorilla diehli*). Evaluating the distribution and abundance of this iconic species (Cross River Gorillas (*Gorilla gorilla diehli*)) in the study areas. Stating the historical review of Cross-River Gorilla (*Gorilla gorilla Diehli*), scientific classification of Cross-River Gorilla (*Gorilla gorilla Diehli*), Description of Cross-River Gorilla (*Gorilla gorilla Diehli*), vegetation of the Park, drainage pattern of the Park, Method of data collection which was line transect method using Drones, trap cameras, and digital cameras. And the Student's T-test (Test of Independent Means) was used in analyzing the data collected. The study reviews that, the Cross River Gorilla (*Gorilla gorilla diehli*) can only be found within the Okwango Division of Cross-River National Park. And the result also indicated that the population of Cross-River Gorilla in the park is critically endangered as recorded with a low population density of 2.0 individuals per km². The result also review that the population status is decreasing at a high rate, and encroachment into the Park has been due to social and economic motives, with widespread poverty in the support zone communities of the park resulting in uncontrolled exploitation of the natural resources. And concludes that, the realization of biodiversity conservation in the park depends on poverty alleviation, provision of alternative livelihood options and infrastructural development in adjoining communities. Which will enable the local communities to appreciate the value of the biological resources and consequently support their conservation. And recommended that, there is an urgent need to carry out Research on the home range and feeding habits of Cross River Gorillas in the Park, due to their small population size.

Keywords: *Cross River Gorilla (Gorilla gorilla diehli), Population distribution and abundance, Okwango Division, Cross River National Park, Conservation and biodiversity management, Anthropogenic threats.*

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Introduction

Background of Study

Habitat loss is among the primary causes of biodiversity loss worldwide, (Haddad *et al.*, 2015). Habitat loss is defined as a reduction in the amount of habitat available for species, (Schwitzer *et al.* 2015; Carretero-Pinzón, 2016). Gorillas are one of the most threatened species globally (Schwitzer *et al.* 2015). Their survival depends on our understanding of their ecological habitat. Habitat loss produce a reduction in the amount of habitat available to species, (Haddad *et al.*, 2015). These influence their population dynamics, and risk their extinction, (Haddad *et al.*, 2015). The direction of the effects and magnitude of those effects varies with the scale at which habitat loss is studied and the particular species of concern (Schwitzer *et al.*, 2015; Carretero-Pinzón, 2016).

Habitat loss and fragmentation have been advocated as the main causes of flora and fauna population declines/species extinction in the tropics, (Cristóbal et al. 2007; Maurice, Fuashi, & Zeh, 2019). Accurately modelling these responses can help predict the most effective locations for future protected areas and identify species that are most at risk, greatly aiding conservation efforts (Connolly *et al.*, 2017; Williams, et al., 2021).

The combine action of hunting and habitat loss, accelerated by burgeoning (expansion) human populations and exacerbated in some by disease outbreaks, has led to the endangerment of all the recognised forms of gorillas, (IUCN, 2007). There is little doubt that many, if not most gorilla populations face an uncertain future (Bergl, 2006).

Objectives of Study

The work has two specific aims which are to:

1. Survey the park in order to know the areas of occurrence of Cross River Gorilla (*Gorilla gorilla diehli*).
2. Evaluate the distribution and abundance of Cross River Gorillas in the study areas.

Statement of Problem

National Parks are being destroyed and wildlife species being lost at alarming rate. There is urgent need for continuous assessment of its present status. This will guide conservators and managers of National Parks to make informed decisions that will guide against such loss of species and population decline. However, Gorillas are among the world's most threatened species of primates (Rylands *et al.* 2008a; Schipper *et al.* 2008). However, currently there is paucity (few) information into the effect of habitat loss on the population of these species and whether these effects vary across primate species (Arroyo-Rodriguez *et al.* 2013b). Nonetheless, most studies on Gorillas focus on the effects of patch-scale fragmentation on gorillas and have ignored the influence of habitat loss at broader scales (Arroyo-Rodriguez *et al.*, 2013a) and (Carretero-Pinzón et al., 2015). This is a critical limitation because species' responses to habitat loss and fragmentation are influenced by the scale at which these processes occur, and they are multi-scaled in nature (Arroyo-Rodriguez *et al.*, 2013b; Carretero-Pinzón et al., 2015).

Justification of the Study

An increased human population and the animal trade market still being strong are causing overexploitation, habitat loss and species extinction, (Arroyo-Rodriguez *et al.*, 2013b; Oskarsson, 2014). This has led to the conservation of biodiversity getting more and more attention (Pratt *et al.* 2004; Oskarsson, 2014). The fact that forest and wildlife habitats around protected areas (PAs) are likely to continue deteriorating, as population around protected areas (PAs) continues to increase, (Scholte, 2013).

This has heightened the imperativeness to manage National Parks within the land use dynamics of their setting. This research work will therefore be additional study towards providing current population data on Cross-River Gorilla (*Gorilla gorilla Diehli*) in the study areas for effective conservation and management. This research will be of benefit to conservation organisations, students, research institutions among others.

Scope of the Study

The study is limited to Cross-River National Park in Cross River State, Nigeria. The study assessed Cross-River Gorillas (*Gorilla gorilla Diehli*) distribution and abundance in the study area.

Literature Review

Historical Review of Cross-River Gorilla (*Gorilla gorilla Diehli*)

There are two (2) major species of gorillas. The western gorilla and the eastern gorilla, (IUCN, 2005). The western gorillas are divided into two sub-species: Cross River gorillas, and the western lowland gorillas. The Eastern gorillas are divided into Mountain gorillas and the Eastern lowland gorillas, (IUCN, 2005; Silverback Gorilla Tours, n.d.). The Cross-River gorilla (*Gorilla gorilla diehli*) is critically endangered subspecies of the western gorilla (*Gorilla gorilla*), (IUCN, 2005; WikiMili, n.d.). It was named a new species in 1904 by Paul Matschie, a mammalian taxonomist working at the Humboldt University Zoological Museum in Berlin, but its populations were not systematically surveyed until 1987, (Oates *et al.* 2013, and Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences, 2013; WikiMili, n.d.)

Scientific Classification of Cross-River Gorilla (*Gorilla gorilla Diehli*)

The cross-River Gorilla belongs to (WikiMili, n.d.):

Domain: Eukaryota,

Kingdom: Animalia

Phylum: Chordata

Class: Mammalia

Order: Primates

Suborder: Haplorhini

Infraorder: Simiiformes

Family: Hominidae

Subfamily: Homininae

Genus: Gorilla

Species: Gorilla gorilla

Subspecies: Gorilla gorilla Diehli,

Trinomial name (biological taxonomic name) Gorilla gorilla diehli, (Matschie *et al.*, 1904).

Description of Cross-River Gorilla (*Gorilla gorilla Diehli*)

The Cross-River gorilla was first described as a new species of the western gorilla by Paul Matschie, a mammalian taxonomist, in 1904, Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences, (2013). Its morphological distinctiveness was confirmed in 1987, (Stump *et al.*1998). Subsequent analyses of cranial and tooth morphology, long bone proportions and distribution demonstrated the distinctiveness of the Cross-River

gorilla and it was described as a distinct subspecies in 2000 (Sarmiento *et al.*, 2000, Stumpf *et al.* 2002; WikiMili, n.d.). When comparing the Cross-River gorilla to western lowland gorillas, they have noticeably smaller palates, smaller cranial vaults, and shorter skulls. The Cross-River gorilla is not known to differ much in terms of body size or limb and bone length from western lowland gorillas. However, measurements taken from a male suggest that they have shorter hands and feet and have a larger opposability index than western lowland gorillas, (Sarmiento *et al.*, 2000; WikiMili, n.d.).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The Study Area

Cross River National Park (CRNP) is situated between latitudes 05°05'N and 06°29'N and longitudes 08°15'E and 09°30'E in Cross River State, south-eastern Nigeria. The Park has two separate sections, Okwangwo division established in 1991 and Oban division established in 1988, (Ezebilo, 2013). The park has a total area of about 4,000km², most of which consists of primary moist tropical rainforests in the North and Central parts, with mangrove swamps on the coastal zones. Parts of the park belong to the Guinea-Congolian region, with a closed canopy and scattered emergent trees reaching 40-50 meters in height, (Nigeria National Park Service, 2015).

Figure 1. Map of Nigeria showing Cross River State, showing the study Locations

Source: Field Survey, (2025).

The Park was established by the Federal Ministry Government Decree in 1991, with the Cross-River gorilla chosen as the theme animal, (Laura, 2013). The park is considered a part of the Guineo-Congolian biodiversity hotspot (Ezebilo, 2013; Olory, 2018). It covers an area of approximately 4,000 km² that harbours mainly humid tropical rainforest and swamps (Olory, 2018).

The biological uniqueness of south-eastern Nigeria is exceptional for Cross River National Park (CRNP), which houses one of the oldest tropical rainforests in Africa, and the last remaining rainforest in Nigeria (Nneji, et al., 2021). Previous studies estimated the vegetation to have evolved over 60 million years ago, with more than 2500 plant, 600 bird, 70 snake, and 100 mammal species (Ezebilo, 2013; Nneji, et al.,

2021). Approximately 90% of all Nigerian butterflies and roughly 30% of butterfly species in sub-Saharan Africa occur in Park, (Nneji, et al., 2021).

The park was first proposed in 1965, but serious planning did not start until 1988. The World Wide Fund for Nature - UK played a leading role for the plan to establish the park in two divisions separated by farmland and the Cross-River valley, with a budget of \$49.9 million. The plan envisaged villagers in the buffer zone being involved in running the park and being given development aid, (John, 2002; Wikipedia contributor, n.d.).

The original plan was not fully implemented, and the park established in 1991 only included existing forest reserves. After a small amount of initial aid, the funding dried up and the villagers became hostile to the park administration, (John, 2002; Wikipedia contributor, n.d.). An amending decree in 1999 converted the Nigerian National Park Service, which runs the park, into a paramilitary outfit with increased powers, (Laura, 2003; Wikipedia contributor, n.d.).

The Oban Hills Division is 2,800 km² in area, centred on coordinates 5°25'0"N 8°35'0"E, (BirdLife International, 2010; Enuoh, & Ogogo, 2018). The division shares a long border with Korup National Park in the Republic of Cameroon, forming a single protected ecological zone, (Nigeria National Park Service, 2013; Enuoh, & Ogogo, 2018). The division has a rugged terrain, rising from 100m in the river valleys to over 1,000m in the mountains. The soils are highly vulnerable to leaching and erosion where stripped of plant cover. The rainy season lasts from March to November, with annual rainfall of over 3,500mm. The northern part is drained by the Cross river and its tributaries. The southern parts are drained by the Calabar, Kwa and Korup rivers, (BirdLife International, 2010; Wikipedia contributor, n.d.).

The division is mostly covered with lowland rainforest. Typical tree species include *Musanga cecropioides* the African corkwood tree or umbrella tree, *Iringia gabonensis* bush mango *Berlinia confusa*, *Coula edulis*, *Hannoa klaineana*, *Klainedoxa gabonensis* African mahogany and red ironwood, (BirdLife International, 2010; Wikipedia contributor, n.d.). About 1,568 plant species have been identified, of which 77 are endemic to Nigeria, (Nigeria National Park Service, 2013; Wikipedia contributor, n.d.). These include 1,303 flowering plants, 141 lichens and 56 moss species, (BirdLife International, 2010). Torben Larsen collected almost 600 species of butterfly in the Oban division in 1995, and estimated that there may be 950 species in total in the division, (John, 2002; Wikipedia contributor, n.d.).

Okwangwo division is centred on coordinates 6°17'00"N 9°14'00"E. It is made up of the former Boshi, Okwangwo and Boshi Extension Forest Reserves, (Uwem, 1997; Enuoh, & Ogogo, 2018). The division has an area of about 920 km² at an altitude of 150 - 1,700m above sea level. It is separated from the Oban division to the south by about 50km of disturbed rainforest. It lies south-west of the Obudu Plateau and immediately to the east of the Afi River Forest Reserve, separated from this reserve by the Mbe Mountains Community Forest, (BirdLife International, 2010; Enuoh, & Ogogo, 2018).

The Takamanda Forest Reserve in the Republic of Cameroon shares a border with the Okwangwo division to the east, (BirdLife International, 2010; Enuoh, & Ogogo, 2018). In November 2008 Takamanda was upgraded to a National Park through a joint project with the Wildlife Conservation Society and the government of Cameroon, with protection of the endangered Cross River gorilla a major objective. The 676km² Takamanda National Park will also help conserve forest elephants, chimpanzees, and drills (ScienceDaily, (2008; Enuoh, & Ogogo, 2018).

The ground is rugged, with rocky ridges and outcrops. The highest points are in the Sankwala Mountains in the north (1,700 m) and in the Mbe Mountains in the south-west (1,000m). Annual rainfall may be as much as 4,280 mm, mostly falling in the wet season between March and November. The division is drained by the Oyi, Bemi and Okon rivers, tributaries of the Cross River. The high ridge-tops are covered in montane grasslands, with relict forests in the valleys. Lower down, the division is covered by lowland rainforests, with areas of savanna where humans have destroyed the forests. The soils in the highland

and lowland areas are vulnerable to erosion and leaching when stripped of their plant cover, (BirdLife International, 2010; Enuoh, & Ogogo, 2018).

The park has four departments: Park Protection and Conservation, Ecotourism, Park Engineering and Maintenance, and Finance and Administration. In 2010, 250 of the total 320 personnel worked in Park Protection and Conservation, mostly male due to the rigors of the job, based at twelve ranger stations. This number is inadequate given the size of the territory to be patrolled. Despite attempts at training, many of the rangers are poorly qualified and are dissatisfied with pay, equipment, motivation and career prospects (Wikipedia contributor, n.d.).

Vegetation of the Park

The park consists of primary moist tropical rainforests in the North and Central parts, with mangrove swamps on the coastal zones. Parts of the park belong to the Guinea-Congolian region, with a closed canopy and scattered emergent trees reaching 40 or 50 meters in height, (Cross River National Park, 2014; Ezebilo, 2013). The park has one of the oldest rainforests in Africa, and has been identified as a biodiversity hot spot, (Cross River National Park, 2014). The Park has two divisions Oban and Okwango.

The Oban division is known to harbour 1,568 species of plants of which 77 species are endemic to Nigeria, three new records for Nigeria and one probably new to science. (Conor and Martin, 1989). Several other vulnerable plants including timber species, NTFPs (Non timber forest products), medicinal plants, among others also abound in the Park. Of interest are medicinal plant species, *Anceistocladus korupensis*, which is suspected to have potent ingredient for the cure of the dreaded HIV/AIDS. And *Prunus africana* known to have potency for cure of prostate cancer (Olory, 2018). The division is mostly covered with lowland rainforest. Typical tree species include *Musanga cecropioides*, the African corkwood tree or umbrella tree, *Iringia gabonensis* bush mango *Berlinia confusa*, *Coula edulis*, *Hannoa klaineana*, *Klainedoxa gabonensis*, African mahogany and red ironwood (Wikipedia contributor, n.d.).

While as in the Okwango division Obot *et al.*, (1996) recorded a total of 1,545 plant specimens representing 98 families in Okwangwo Division alone. Of these, six (6) were said to be new records to Nigeria and four probably new to science. The new records to Nigeria are: *Asplenium cornutum* (Aspleniaceae), *Arthropteris monocarpa* (Davalliaceae); *Bulbophyllum bequaertii* (Orchidaceae); *Bulbophyllum odicum* (Orchidaceae); *Disperis nitida* (Orchidaceae) and *Habenaria obovata* (Orchidaceae), while the possible species new to science include: *Trydactyle* spp (Orchidaceae); *Uapaca* spp (Euphorbiaceae); *Habenaria* spp. (Orchidaceae) and *Afrocalathea flavida* spp. (Maranthaceae), (Obot *et al.*, 1996; Olory, 2018).

Drainage Pattern of the Park

The Park is divided into two, Oban division and Okwango division. The Oban division has a rugged terrain, rising from 100m in the river valleys to over 1,000 m in the mountains. The soils are highly vulnerable to leaching and erosion where stripped of plant cover. The rainy season lasts from March to November, with annual rainfall of over 3,500mm. The northern part is drained by the Cross river and its tributaries. The southern parts are drained by the Calabar, Kwa and Korup rivers, (Cross River National Park, 2014; Onen, et al., 2019).

While as in the Okwango division the ground is rugged, with rocky ridges and outcrops. The highest points are in the Sankwala Mountains in the north (1,700 m) and in the Mbe Mountains in the south-west (1,000m). Annual rainfall may be as much as 4,280mm, mostly falling in the wet season between March and November. The division is drained by the Oyi, Bemil and Okon rivers, tributaries of the Cross River. The high ridge-tops are covered in montane grasslands, with relict forests in the valleys. Lower down, the division is covered by lowland rainforests, with areas of savanna where humans have destroyed the forests. The soils in the highland and lowland areas are vulnerable to erosion and leaching when stripped of their plant cover, (Cross River National Park, 2014; Onen, et al., 2019).

Method of Data Collection

A guided reconnaissance survey was carried out from September 1st, 2023 to September 14th, 2023 using line transect Method as described by, (Adendem *et al.*, 2021). To be able to cover a good representation of the large study area, reconnaissance walks and direct search were carried out in two (2) sections of the park, Okwango Range and Anape Range respectively. During this census, the observers were equipped with binoculars, digital cameras, and a field data sheet to record the following information's: Transect number, Distance walked by observer, Distance of observer to animals sighted, Number of animals sighted. This was done once in a month twice in a day for each census day from 6:00am to 10:00am and from 2:00pm to 6:00pm of each censured day.

Drones, trap cameras, and digital cameras were used to take photographs of the Gorilla species as well as signs of anthropogenic activities while binoculars were used to observe Gorillas away from each transect. During this survey, deviations from predetermined directions were kept to a minimum except where terrain or vegetation made it impossible to continue in a straight line. Where difficult terrain were encountered; such as rivers and high rocky mountains requiring large deviations a transect walk ends and another began on the other side of the obstruction as described by (Adendem *et al.*, 2020; Agaldo, Gwom, & Apeverga, 2013).

Line Transect Method

The study area (Okwango division) of Cross River National Park, was divided into 20 research blocks of 20km² each. This was to avoid bias in the study area selection and data collection on Gorillas since the study area is made up of different vegetation types affected by human activities. The line transects technique as described by (Adendem *et al.*, 2021) was employed (Maurice, Fuashi, & Zeh, 2019).

In each block, a 1-kilometre square transect was established in selected sample areas taking into consideration the landscape configuration. A total of twenty (20) line transects were established in the study areas with the aid of GPS. The starting points of all transects was from the forested areas. About two (2) hours was used to walk on each transect, as described by (Adendem *et al.*, 2021; Maurice, Fuashi, & Zeh, 2019) looking ahead and sideways to detect the Gorillas, and occasionally using binoculars to determine Gorillas group sizes. Each transect was walked by two observers, within the range of 50m on both sides of the central line across all the sample areas maintaining a straight line so as to have little or no effects on the perpendicular distance estimation (Maurice, Fuashi, & Zeh, 2019).

During this transect-walk, all gorillas sighted, vocalizations, signs (dung, resting places, foot prints, carcasses, nest, and food remains) were recorded (Maurice, Fuashi, & Zeh, 2019). To ensure that perpendicular distances are estimated accurately, observers were trained on evaluating distances prior to the onset of the study (Leca *et al.* 2013; Maurice, Fuashi, & Zeh, 2019).

Primary data were collected by recording every gorilla group and individual observed along transect. Data was collected by establishing the number of individuals per group (Carretero-Pinzón, 2016).

Census was conducted once in a month twice in a day. Every last week of a new month, from 6:00am to 10:00am hours and again at 2:00pm to 6:00pm hours on the same day. Surveys was not conducted in heavy rain. Transects were walked at approximately 0.5km/h with only Cross River gorilla species recorded. When a gorilla group is visually detected, a minimum of 10 minutes was taken to count the group members and determine group composition (number of males, females and immature). And the time of detection was also recorded. The coordinates of each observation were registered using a GPS. All observations and species identifications were aided by binoculars, and primate species classification following the guide by DeFler, (2010), and Mittermeier *et al.* (2013) and Carretero-Pinzón, (2016). This continue for a period of twenty four (24) months. Starting from September, 2023 to September, 2025.

Data Analysis

The Student's T-test (Test of Independent Means) was used, to compare the result obtained from the two censured areas of the Park. That is Anape and Okwango Ranges respectively. The perpendicular distances measured was used to estimate a detection function (that is, the probability that a Cross River Gorilla is detected, as a decreasing function of its distance from the line). This permit the calculation of the Gorillas density (groups of Gorillas) in the study area. In order to provide estimates of the Gorillas density and abundance in the study areas, the computer software program distance 7.2 was used to estimate the mean group size, and average number of individuals detected (that is seen not heard) during the encounters of different groups. Individual Gorillas densities were calculated using a combination of transects surveys and total count in areas where Gorillas had been seen (Maurice, Fuashi, & Zeh, 2019).

The Population Density (PD) was estimated using the Formula

$$PD = \frac{\text{Number of gorillas sited}}{\text{Area Covered(km}^2\text{)}} \quad (1)$$

The encounter rate (n/L) was define as the number of groups detected per unit length of transect, that is per distance walked or kilometre walked. The effect of ecological factors on the Gorillas distribution was examine (habitat types, fragment size, vegetation structure, landscape) and other factors contributing to the Gorillas distribution. Factors such as: weather, season, and time of sight. The test criterion is given below (Maurice, Fuashi, & Zeh, 2019):

$$t' = \frac{|x_1 - x_2|}{sp^2 \left(\frac{1}{n_1} + \frac{1}{n_2} \right)} \quad (2)$$

where;

x_1 = Mean density of first census

x_2 = Mean density of second census

sp^2 = Pooled variance

n_1 = Frequency of sight of first census

n_2 = Frequency of sight of second census

$$\text{Pooled variance } sp^2 = \frac{\left[\sum x_1^2 - \frac{(\sum x_1)^2}{n_1} \right] + \left[\sum x_2^2 - \frac{(\sum x_2)^2}{n_2} \right]}{(n_1 - 1) + (n_2 - 1)} \quad (3)$$

Or

$$\frac{(n_1 - 1)s_1^2 + (n_2 - 1)s_2^2}{(n_1 - 1) + (n_2 - 1)} \quad (4)$$

Where:

S_1^2 and S_2^2 are variances for the first and second censuses respectively.

The data analyzed is presented in tables, charts and figures as shown in the result.

Results

The Population Density, Distribution and Abundance of Cross River Gorilla (*Gorilla gorilla Diehli*) In the Study Locations

The percentage of gorilla sightings recorded in the Anape and Okwango Ranges during the dry and rainy seasons indicate that 100% of sightings occurred in the Anape Range, whereas no individuals were sighted in the Okwango Range across the two seasonal periods. This pattern shows a clear spatial disparity in gorilla distribution between the two study locations, irrespective of seasonal variations. The presence of gorillas in Anape throughout both dry and rainy seasons may be indicative of favorable ecological conditions, such as the availability of forage resources, suitable nesting habitats, and lower levels of anthropogenic disturbance. The absence of sightings in Okwango raises important ecological and conservation concerns. Possible explanations include habitat degradation, higher human activity levels (e.g., farming, logging, or hunting pressure), or broader ecological shifts that may have driven gorilla populations away from the area.

The findings show the significance of site-specific ecological assessments in understanding the Cross River Gorillas distribution patterns. This further highlights the need for targeted conservation strategies in Okwango to restore suitable habitat conditions, mitigate human pressures, and potentially encourage the recolonization of gorilla populations. Additionally, the results point to the value of long-term and multi-seasonal monitoring to validate the persistence of these patterns and to distinguish between temporary absences and long-term range shifts.

Figure 2. The Number (%) of Gorillas Sighted by Season in the Study Locations

Source: Field Survey, (2025)

Figure 3 shows the relative distribution and sighting distance of gorillas encountered in the Anape and Okwango Ranges across different observation periods and ecological conditions. The result shows that during the dry season, evening encounters at distances of 30m and 45m recorded a population density of 2.0 individuals per km² in Anape, while no individual was sighted in Okwango within the same period.

This pattern indicates a pronounced spatial heterogeneity in gorilla presence between the two ranges, with Anape sustaining observable populations while Okwango exhibited an absence of gorilla activity in the sampled transects. The observed disparity may be attributed to differences in habitat quality, food resource availability, or anthropogenic pressures across the ranges. In particular, the dry season often imposes constraints on forage resources, potentially concentrating gorilla populations in areas with more favorable vegetation and microhabitat conditions, such as those provided by Anape. However, the absence of gorilla sightings in Okwango could reveal habitat degradation, seasonal migration, or disturbance from human activities.

Figure 3. Sighting Distance (per km²) of Cross River Gorillas Sighted in Anape and Okwango Range
 Source: Field Survey, (2025)

Figure 4 presents a comparative analysis of indirect field indices associated with the presence of Cross River gorillas in the two ranges (Anape and Okwango Range) within the Cross River National Park. The indices evaluated include calls, dung, fur, and nests, which are standard signs used in primate field surveys to infer species presence, behavior, and habitat use when direct sightings are rare.

In the Anape Range, nests were the most frequently recorded indices, accounting for 66.7% of all indirect signs observed. This implies that the area serves as an active or recent resting or nesting site for Cross River gorillas. Nest-building behavior is a well-documented trait in great apes, often indicating night-time use or temporary settlement areas. Calls were the second most prevalent index, representing 22.2% of all signs. Vocalizations are critical for gorilla communication, especially in dense forests, and indicate active movement or group cohesion behaviors. Dung was also recorded (11.1%), which is a direct sign of feeding activity and recent presence. The presence of dung can be used for diet analysis and genetic studies, further confirming gorilla presence. Fur, however, was not observed (0.0%) in Anape Range, which implies that although the gorillas are using the area, they are not engaging in behaviors that result in fur shedding, or such signs were simply not encountered during the survey.

There were no signs of calls, dung, or nests recorded in the Okwango Range all at 0.0%, indicating a possible absence or very low recent activity of Cross River gorillas in this range during the survey period. Fur was recorded at 100% in Okwango Range, which is high and may suggest either historical or isolated movement through the area where fur was shed, potentially due to rubbing against trees, grooming, or territorial behavior. The exclusive detection of fur in Okwango, with the absence of other more dynamic

indices like calls or nests, indicate that the gorillas do not currently inhabit the area regularly, but might use it sporadically or as a migratory corridor.

Figure 4. Indirect Indices of Cross-River Gorillas Encountered in the Study Areas
Source: Field Survey, (2025)

Discussion

Understanding the effects of habitat loss on the distribution and abundance of species remains a leading question in ecology. For many years, explanations adopted either an ecological or an evolutionary standpoint, that is, whether species distribution and abundance was subject to particular environmental determinants as inferred from correlative models or to differences in diversification timing and rates, respectively (Maurice, Fuashi, & Zeh, 2019). The report on the population density indicates differences between the two ranges.

The Cross River Gorilla exhibit a lower population densities (2.0 individual per km²) in Anape Range, and 0.0 individual per km² in Okwango Range. This variation in density revealed the spatial and ecological differences between the two Ranges and emphasize the importance of habitat availability and resource distribution in shaping the Gorillas population dynamics in the study area. These findings are in agreement with that of Adendem et al., (2020). Where they assess primates population abundance in Yaa-iwa and Apinu-Igede Forest Reserves in Benue state, Nigeria. And disagreed with other studies on the effects of selective logging on forest composition and growth dynamics in semi-deciduous forests in Western Equatorial Africa (Gourlet-Fleury et al., 2013ab).

The temporal variation in the two Ranges shows an increase in gorillas' density during the morning 2.0 individuals/km². The gorillas in this areas were more active or visible during the morning, possibly due to shifts in behaviour, such as foraging patterns or favourable environmental conditions such as low temperature indicating a significant contrast in the temporal activity patterns between the two ranges. These report agreed with that of Uloko and Adendem, (2020) were they stated categorically that, the lower the temperature, the higher the number of primates sighted, and the higher the temperature the lower the number.

Seasonally, the two ranges experiences a decline in gorillas density from the wet season (2.0 individual/km²) to the dry season (2.0 individuals/km²) showing a low presence. Indicating that both the wet season and dry season offers better resources or more favourable conditions for Gorillas in the two ranges. This low density, could be attributed to unfavourable environmental condition. This report is in agreement with that of Uloko and Adendem, (2020). Where low densities of 0.02 individual/km² and 1.68 individual/km² in the rainy/wet season were recorded in a disturbed savannah zone of Iyaa-iwa

and Ipinu-Igede Forest Reserves in Benue state, Nigeria. And disagreed with the findings of Oates *et al.*, (1990), where a relatively high densities were recorded in a more disturbed secondary forest of the Tiwai Island wildlife Sanctuary in Sierra Leone, (Oates et al. 1990), and that of Buzzard, (2006) in mature forest in the Tai National Park, Cote d'Ivoire.

The frequency distribution of individual Gorilla species encounters in the two ranges indicated that the Cross-River Gorillas, *Gorilla gorilla diebli* population is critically endangered. Showing a relatively lower frequency in only one range. This findings disagreed with the findings of McClean, (2005) where he encountered four individuals of the Cross-River Gorilla at Afi mountain sanctuary in Cross River state.

The low encounter rate of the Cross-River Gorilla (*Gorilla gorilla diebli*) in the study areas could be as a result of anthropogenic activities which make them hide in areas that they cannot be seeing easily or possibly because of hunting pressure on this iconic specie. These findings is in accordance with that of Elkan et al., (2006) he stated that Poaching remains the greatest threat to wildlife in many regions, and the spatial-temporal relationship between expanding road networks and increased illegal hunting pressure within the study areas is both pervasive and instructive. Since the Park's creation, effective management of poaching pressure in the surrounding logging concessions should be a priority to protect the integrity of the core areas. Law enforcement patrols can lower threat levels to protected areas (Stokes et al., 2010; Tranquilli et al., 2014; Morgan, et al., 2019).

The differences in the frequency of Cross River Gorilla encountered between the two ranges, implies that the species dynamics and distribution differs between the two Ranges, possibly influenced by factors such as food availability, social structures, and habitat preferences. These patterns in temporal and seasonal variation show the adaptive strategies of Gorilla species in response to environmental factors, with potential influences from food availability, temperature, and social behavior influencing the Cross River Gorilla activity across different times and seasons.

Lack of fruits and Rainfall could be the possible reason why only one individual of Cross River Gorilla species was sighted during the rainy season while as high temperature could be the reason why only one individual was sighted in the dry season. While as the reason for the dropped in population in dry season could also be as a result of open vegetation in dry season or insufficient food materials such as fruits and lack of water.

This result agreed with the findings of Adendem et al., (2020) in their survey of primates in Iyaaaiwa and Ipinu-Igede Forest Reserves in Benue state, Nigeria, where they stated categorically that the more the rate of rainfall the higher the number of primates sighted and the higher the temperature, the lower the primates sighted and, the lower the temperature, the higher the number of primates sighted.

These suggest that, the Anape range provides a more favourable environment for the Gorilla species, supporting a more evenly distributed community. This report agreed with that of Husson et al., (2009) where he stated clarely that Industrial logging is projected to continue at 30-year rotation cycles in most of Western Africa and so the fate of many species is unknown. Repeated removal of timber even at low intensity levels can degrade the quality of habitat over time therefore reducing the availability of such species in an area (Lindenmayer and Franklin, 2002; Morgan, et al., 2019), and could have negative consequences for the gorillas as shown in the degraded forests of Asia (Husson et al., 2009; Morgan, et al., 2019).

The finding on relative frequency, relative density, and conservation status of Gorilla species distribution and ecological roles across Okwango and Anape Range imply that, though only only one Range supported a total number of two (2) individuals, the ecological characteristics of each species fauna and flora within these areas and their conservation concerns differed. There are significant differences in relative density, and the overall ecological importance of different Gorilla species.

The relative density values for each gorilla species shows differences between the two ranges. For instance, the relative density of Cross River Gorilla, *Gorilla gorilla diehli* is 0.0 individuals/km² in Okwango Range, but it increases to 2.0 individual/km² in Anape Range, indicating a higher abundance in the Anape range. This report is in accordance with the findings of Remis, (2000). He reported a density of 1.52 individuals/km² at Sangha Reserve, Central African Republic. This report disagreed with the findings of Usongo, (1998). He reported a density of 2.50 individuals/km² recorded at the proposed Lobeke Forest Reserve in Cameroon.

However, the result from the present study disagreed with that of 0.44 individuals/km² recorded in Gabon (Usongo and Williamson,1998), 0.70 individuals/km² recorded for Rio Muni Island in Equatorial Guinea (Fa et al., 1995) and higher than 0.20 individuals/ km² reported by BowensJones and Pendry (1999) in Motaba Region of the Republic of Congo (Remis, 2001). This findings further agreed with that of Romdal et al., (2013) were he reported that contemporary conditions and events such as anthropogenic changes in habitat and climate continue to influence species diversity by removing species from some areas and adding them to others. As niches are generally conserved over large time-scales, species tend to have a limited ability to respond to rapid changes in environmental conditions. This emphasizes the relevance of identifying the environmental drivers of patterns of species richness, as they indicate the key conditions that are expected to affect species richness following ongoing environmental changes (Maurice, Fuashi, & Zeh, 2019).

The critical endangered status of Cross River Gorilla in the study areas could be as a result of poaching activities such as hunting, logging among others. This report is in accordance with that of Elkan *et al.*, (2006) they reported that, Poaching remains the greatest threat to wildlife status, and the spatial-temporal relationship between expanding road networks and increased illegal hunting pressure within different ecosystems.

The indirect evidence revealed from this finding implies a greater variety of Gorilla species present in the Anape Range compared to Okwango Range. While vocalizations were the predominant form of detection, dung was more commonly found in Anape Range, and fur was recorded in only a few instances. The lack of indirect evidence in some areas suggests either a lower abundance or reduced detectability within that range, which may be influenced by hunting levels, habitat characteristics, resource availability, or behaviour patterns. This findings agreed with that of Potapov *et al.*, (2017) and Bermejo et al., (2006) they both reported that threat that are exacerbated by reduction of direct and indirect indicies is considerable spatial overlap between animals and humans and the dramatic reductions of fauna indices in some regions of northern Congo have been attributed to excessive hunting levels.

Conclusion

This research finds out that, the Cross-River Gorilla (*Gorilla gorilla diehli*) presence is known only at Okwango division of Cross River National Park. And the population status is decreasing at a high rate (Critically endangered) on IUCN list. Encroachment into Okwango division of Cross River National Park has been due to social and economic motives, with widespread poverty in the support zone communities of the park resulting in uncontrolled exploitation of the natural resources (Adetola, & Adetoro, 2014). Therefore hindering the long term sustainability of biodiversity (Adetola, & Adetoro, 2014).

Thus, the realization of biodiversity conservation in the park depends on poverty alleviation, provision of alternative livelihood options and infrastructural development in adjoining communities. This will enable the local communities to appreciate the value of the biological resources and consequently support their conservation (Adetola, & Adetoro, 2014).

This finding revealed that, the two Ranges (Okwango and Anape) are low in Cross River Gorillas population 2.0 individual in Anape Range and 0.0 individual in the Okwango Range.

Further research should be carryout on their spatial distribution and abundance potential in the study area in order to ensure fast recovery of this iconic species (Japheth, Ugbe, & Alfa, 2023). Also, the Federal Government should re-strengthen the policies protecting the areas in order to ensure sustainable biodiversity management, due to the roles the protected areas play in climate change mitigation which cannot be overemphasize in Nigeria. Strict policies could also improve the growth and productivity of forest ecosystems of the study areas (Japheth, Ugbe, & Alfa, 2023).

Recommendations

Based on the findings above, the following recommendations are made:

1. There is an urgent need to carry out Research on the home range and feeding habits of Cross River Gorilla in Okwango Range, due to their small population sizes.
2. Land surveys should be carried out to determine the rate of encroachment into the Park by loggers and farmers.
3. Government, NGOs and individuals should encourage research on Cross River Gorillas through adequate logistics and financial support to researchers.

Contribution to Knowledge

The research provided ecological indices on Cross River Gorilla (*Gorilla gorilla diehli's*) distribution, abundance and availability in both Ranges (Anape and Okwango) including their population densities of 2.0 individual/km² in Anape Range and 0.0 indivial/km² in Okwango Range.

References

- Adendem, M. N., Uloko, I. J., & Orsar, T. J. (2020). *Effect of anthropogenic activities on primates in Ipinu-Igede and Yaaina Forest Reserves in Benue State, Nigeria*. In Wildlife Society of Nigeria (WISON), Makurdi 2020.
- Adetola, B., & Adetoro, A. O. (2014). Threats to biodiversity conservation in Cross River National Park, Nigeria. *International Journal of Conservation Science*, 5(4), 547–552.
- Agaldo, J. A., Gwom, T. G., & Apeverga, P. T. (2013, March 18). *Survey of Nigeria-Cameroon chimpanzee in the Oban Hills, Nigeria* (Project report No. 0141711). Cross River National Park & Wildlife Conservation Society, Nigeria.
- Arroyo-Rodríguez, V., Cuesta-del Moral, E., Mandujano, S., Chapman, C. A., Reyna-Hurtado, R., & Fahrig, L. (2013a). Assessing habitat fragmentation effects on primates: The importance of evaluating questions at the correct scale. In L. K. Marsh & C. A. Chapman (Eds.), *Primates in fragments: Ecology and conservation* (pp. 13–28). *Developments in Primatology: Progress and Prospects*. Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-8839-2_2
- Arroyo-Rodríguez, V., González-Perez, I. M., Garmendia, A., Solà, M., & Estrada, A. (2013b). The relative impact of forest patch and landscape attributes on black howler populations in the fragmented Lacandona rainforest, Mexico. *Landscape Ecology*, 28(10), 1717–1727. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10980-013-9929-2>

Bergl, R. A. (2006). *Conservation biology of the Cross River gorilla (Gorilla gorilla diehli)* (Doctoral dissertation, City University of New York). ProQuest Dissertations Publishing. Publication No. AAI3232001. ISBN: 9780542850790

Bermejo, M., Rodríguez-Teijeiro, J. D., Illera, G., Barroso, A., Vilà, C., & Walsh, P. D. (2006). Ebola outbreak killed 5000 gorillas. *Science*, *314*(5805), 1564. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1133105>

BirdLife International. (2010). *Important Bird Areas factsheet: Cross River National Park: Oban Division*. Retrieved November 27, 2025, from <https://datazone.birdlife.org/site/factsheet/6740-cross-river-national-park-oban-division>

Bowen-Jones, E., & Pendry, S. (1999). The threat to primates and other mammals from the bushmeat trade in Africa, and how this threat could be diminished. *Oryx*, *33*(3), 233–246. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1365-3008.1999.00066.x>

Buzzard, P. J. (2006). Ranging patterns in relation to seasonality and frugivory among *Cercopithecus campbelli*, *C. petaurista*, and *C. diana* in the Tai Forest. *International Journal of Primatology*, *27*(2), 559–573. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10764-006-9028-1>

Carretero-Pinzón, X. (2016). *Conservation planning for primate communities in rapidly transforming landscapes* (Doctoral dissertation, The University of Queensland, School of Geography, Planning and Environmental Management). The University of Queensland. <https://espace.library.uq.edu.au/view/UQ:398697>

Carretero-Pinzón, X., Defler, T. R., McAlpine, C. A., & Rhodes, J. R. (2016). What do we know about the effect of patch size on primate species across life history traits? *Biodiversity and Conservation*, *25*(1), 37–66. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10531-015-1028-z>

Clark, C. J., Poulsen, J. R., Malonga, R., & Elkan, P. W., Jr. (2009). Logging concessions can extend the conservation estate for Central African tropical forests. *Conservation Biology*, *23*(5), 1281–1293. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1523-1739.2009.01243.x>

Coner, J., & Martin, P. (1989). Oban Project: WWF Education Sector study; WWF Oban feasibility study.

Connolly, S. R., Keith, S. A., Colwell, R. K., & Rahbek, C. (2017). Process, mechanism, and modeling in macroecology. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution*, *32*(11), 835–844. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2017.08.011>

Cristóbal-Azkarate, J., & Arroyo-Rodríguez, V. (2007). Diet and activity pattern of howler monkeys in Los Tuxtlas, Mexico: Effects of habitat fragmentation and implications for conservation. *American Journal of Primatology*, *69*(9), 1013–1029. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ajp.20420>

Cross River National Park (2014). *Nigeria National Park Service*. Archived March 14, 2012. Retrieved November 5, 2015.

Enuoh, O., & Ogogo, A. (2018). Cross River National Park and communities: Is authoritarian park protection the answer? *Journal of Sustainable Development*, *11*(5), 212–212. <https://doi.org/10.5539/jsd.v11n5p212>

Ezebilo, E. E. (2013). Nature conservation in Cross River National Park, south-east Nigeria: Promoting collaboration between local people and conservation authorities. *International Journal of Biodiversity Science, Ecosystem Services & Management*, *9*(3), 215–224. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21513732.2013.813586>

Ezebilo, E. E. (2013). Nature conservation in Cross River National Park, south-east Nigeria: promoting collaboration between local people and conservation authorities. *International Journal of Biodiversity Science, Ecosystem Services & Management*, *9*(3), 215–224. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21513732.2013.813586>

Fa, J. E., Peres, C. A., & Meeuwig, J. (2002). Bushmeat exploitation in tropical forests: An intercontinental comparison. *Conservation Biology*, *16*(1), 232–237. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1523-1739.2002.00275.x>

- Gourlet-Fleury, S., Mortier, F., Fayolle, A., Baya, F., Ouédraogo, D., Bénédet, F., & Picard, N. (2013). Tropical forest recovery from logging: A 24-year silvicultural experiment from Central Africa. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, 368(1625), 20120302. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rstb.2012.0302>
- Haddad, N. M., Brudvig, L. A., Clobert, J., Davies, K. F., Gonzalez, A., Holt, R. D., ... & Townshend, J. R. (2015). Habitat fragmentation and its lasting impact on Earth's ecosystems. *Science Advances*, 1(2), e1500052. <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.1500052>
- Hanson, T., Brooks, T. M., Da Fonseca, G. A. B., Hoffmann, M., Lamoreux, J. F., Machlis, G., ... & Pilgrim, J. D. (2009). Warfare in biodiversity hotspots. *Conservation Biology*, 23(3), 578–587. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1523-1739.2009.01166.x>
- Ite, U. E. (1997). Small farmers and forest loss in Cross River National Park, Nigeria. *The Geographical Journal*, 163(1), 47–56.
- IUCN. (2005). The IUCN Red List of Threatened Species. Retrieved March 12, 2007, from <https://www.iucnredlist.org>
- Japheth, D. H., Ugbe, J. A., & Alfa, J. I. (2023). Alpha Diversity and Species Status of Uneven Forests in Eco-Zones of Taraba State, Nigeria, *Journal of Bioresource Management*, 10 (3).
- Leca, J.-B., Gunst, N., Rompis, A., Soma, G., Putra, I. G. A. A., & Wandia, I. N. (2013). Population density and abundance of ebony leaf monkeys (*Trachypithecus auratus*) in West Bali National Park, Indonesia. *Primate Conservation*, 26(1), 133–144. <https://doi.org/10.1896/052.026.0106>
- Lindenmayer, D., Messier, C., & Sato, C. (2016). Avoiding ecosystem collapse in managed forest ecosystems. *Frontiers in Ecology and the Environment*, 14(10), 561–568. <https://doi.org/10.1002/fee.1434>
- Marsh, L. K. (Ed.). (2013). *Primates in fragments: Complexity and resilience*. Springer. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-8839-2>
- Maurice, M. E., Fuashi, N. A., & Zeh, A. F. (2019). The effects of habitat fragmentation on the distribution of primates in the Kimbi-Fungom National Park, North West Region, Cameroon. *MOJ Ecology & Environmental Sciences*, 4(2), 60–68. <https://doi.org/10.15406/mojes.2019.04.00135>
- McClellan, C. J., Lovett, J. C., Kuper, W., Hannah, L., Sommer, J. H., Barthlott, W., ... & Taplin, J. R. D. (2005). African plant diversity and climate change. *Annals of the Missouri Botanical Garden*, 92(2), 139–152. [Stable JSTOR link/DOI if available]
- Morgan, D., Strindberg, S., Winston, W., Stephens, C. R., Traub, C., Ayina, C. E., Ebika, S. T. N., Mayoukou, W., Koni, D., Iyenguet, F., & Sanz, C. M. (2019). Impacts of selective logging and associated anthropogenic disturbance on intact forest landscapes and apes of Northern Congo. *Frontiers in Forests and Global Change*, 2, Article 28. <https://doi.org/10.3389/ffgc.2019.00028>
- Nigeria National Park Service (2015). *Cross River National Park*. Archived March 14, 2012. Retrieved November 5, 2010.
- Nneji, L. M., Adeola, A. C., Adedeji, B. E., & others. (2021). Species richness, distribution pattern, and conservation status of amphibians in Cross River National Park, south-eastern Nigeria. *Biologia*, 76(10), 2573–2588. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11756-021-00751-8>
- Oates, J. F., Anadu, P. A., Gadsby, E. L., & Werre, J. L. (1992). Sclater's guenon—A rare Nigerian monkey threatened by deforestation. *National Geographic Research and Exploration*, 8, 476–491.
- Oates, J. F., Sunderland-Groves, J., Bergl, R., Dunn, A., Nicholas, A., Takang, E., ... & Williamson, E. A. (2007). *Regional action plan for the conservation of the Cross River gorilla (Gorilla gorilla diehli)*. IUCN/SSC Primate Specialist Group and Conservation International.

- Obot, E. A., Ogar, G., Edet, C. A., Olory, C. S., Ayuk, J., & Akongke, C. (1996). Biological inventory in the Okwangwo Division, Cross River National Park: Progress report 1994–1996. April 1996.
- Olory, C. S. (2018). Contributions of Cross River National Park to national development: Prospects and challenges. In *Proceedings of the 6th NSCB Biodiversity Conference* (pp. 309–315). University of Uyo.
- Olory, C. S. (2022). Increasing signs of forest fragmentation in the Cross River National Park in Nigeria: Underlying drivers and need for sustainable responses. *Ecological Indicators*, 108943. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2022.108943>
- Onen, I. I., Aguru, C. U., Iheukwumere, C. C., Olasan, J. O., & Aboh, A. A. (2019). Evaluation of the ecological impact of human settlement on trees in Oban and Okwangwo forests of Cross River National Park, Nigeria. *Asian Journal of Environment & Ecology*, 10(1), 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.9734/ajee/2019/v10i130108>
- Oskarsson, S. (2014). *Community engagement in wildlife conservation* (Master's thesis, Halmstad University, Master's Programme in Applied Environmental Science). Halmstad University.
- Peoples Media Limited. (2015, August 15–16). Weekend edition (Issue). Retrieved January 31, 2022.
- Potapov, P., Hansen, M. C., Laestadius, L., Turubanova, S., Yaroshenko, A., Thies, C., ... & Esipova, E. (2017). The last frontiers of wilderness: Tracking loss of intact forest landscapes from 2000 to 2013. *Science Advances*, 3(1), e1600821. <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.1600821>
- Remis, M. (2001). Preliminary assessment of the impacts of human activities on gorillas (*Gorilla gorilla gorilla*) and other wildlife at Dzanga-Sangha Reserve, Central African Republic. *Oryx*, 34(1), 56–65. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1365-3008.2000.00091.x>
- Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences. (2013). *Gorilla gorilla diehli taxonomy and nomenclature* (PDF). Retrieved October 25, 2013.
- Rylands, A. B., Williamson, E. A., Hoffmann, M., & Mittermeier, R. A. (2008). Primate surveys and conservation assessments. *Oryx*, 42(3), 313–314.
- Sarmiento, E., & Oates, J. F. (2000). The Cross River gorillas: A distinct subspecies, *Gorilla gorilla diehli* Matschie 1904. *American Museum Novitates*, (3304), 1–55. <https://doi.org/10.1206/3304.1>
- Scholte, P. (2011). Towards understanding large mammal population declines in Africa's protected areas: A West-Central African perspective. *Tropical Conservation Science*, 4(1), 1–11.
- Schwitzer, C., Mittermeier, R. A., Rylands, A. B., Chiozza, F., Williamson, E. A., Wallis, J., & Cotton, A. (Eds.). (2015). *Primates in peril: The world's 25 most endangered primates 2014–2016*. IUCN SSC PSG/IPS/CI/Bristol Zoological Society.
- ScienceDaily. (2008, November 28). *New national park protects world's rarest gorilla*. Retrieved November 5, 2010.
- Silverback Gorilla Tours. (n.d.). *Facts about Cross River gorillas: Conservation & endangered status*. Retrieved November 27, 2025, from <https://www.silverbackgorillatours.com/gorilla/facts-about-cross-river-gorillas>
- Stokes, D. L., Hanson, M. F., Oaks, D. D., Straub, J. E., & Ponio, A. V. (2010). Local land-use planning to conserve biodiversity: Planners' perspectives on what works. *Conservation Biology*, 24(2), 450–460. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1523-1739.2009.01356.x>
- Stump, B. W., Hedlin, M. A. H., Pearson, D. C., & Hsu, V. (2002). Characterization of mining explosions at regional distances: Implications with the International Monitoring System. *Reviews of Geophysics*, 40(4), 1011. <https://doi.org/10.1029/1998RG000048>

Terborgh, J. (2002). *Making parks work: Strategies for preserving tropical nature*. Island Press. ISBN 978-1559639057

Uloko, I. J., Orsar, T. J., & Adendem, M. N. (2020). Survey of primates in two selected forest reserves in Benue State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Agriculture, Environment and BioResearch*, 5(3), 77–104. <https://doi.org/10.35410/IJAEB.2020.5508>

Ushongo, L., Seino, R. A., & Focho, D. A. (1998). The trapping of wildlife in the Rumpi Hills Forest Reserve, southwest Cameroon. *Nature et Faune*, 14(1), 3–13.

WikiMili. (n.d.). *Cross River gorilla*. In *WikiMili, the best Wikipedia reader*. Retrieved November 27, 2025, from https://wikimili.com/en/Cross_River_gorilla

Wikipedia contributors. (n.d.). *Cross River gorilla*. In *Wikipedia*. Retrieved November 27, 2025, from <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki?curid=28024638>

Williams, K. A., Slater, H. D., Gillingham, P., & others. (2021). Environmental factors are stronger predictors of primate species' distributions than basic biological traits. *International Journal of Primatology*, 42(3), 404–425. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10764-021-00208-4>

